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PECULIARITIES OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LIFELONG LEARNING POLICY IN TURKEY

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The relevance of the study is due to the fact that in the 21st century, lifelong learning is recognized as one of the key pillars of education, closely intertwined with human development and financial growth. It is determined, that in recent years, major universities, governments and non-governmental organizations around the world continue to discuss the practice of lifelong learning. Being in the process of full membership in the EU, Turkey continues to comply with international norms and standards and comply with the established requirements.

The institutional efforts to support and disseminate adult education in Turkey, strengthen the vocational education and training system in the context of the implementation of the concept of lifelong learning were analyzed. It has been found, that in Turkey, the concept of lifelong has recently been seen as a model of approach to education and training. Turkey has been shown to need a long-term vision and strategy for adult learning as part of a broader lifelong learning strategy in order to increase adult learning opportunities.

The generalization of Turkey's progressive experience revealed the peculiarities of the implementation of lifelong learning policies, namely: ensuring the unity of national culture; implementing a strong policy of justice and equality in education; promotion of civic education; active participation in lifelong learning systems in order to build a competitive knowledge economy for the EU; promoting the literacy skills of Turkish citizens; training of qualified people in need of society; adaptation of non-formal and adult education to lifelong learning.

The generalization of vectors for expanding opportunities for adult learning in Turkey has identified promising areas for adult education in Ukraine, namely: investing in the expansion and diversification of learning spaces or opportunities in the field of lifelong learning; updating programs to support parents of young, children and adolescents; organization of trainings on raising awareness and skills of multi-literacy; recognition of certificates in the process of lifelong learning and non-formal education; conducting research on social consciousness for lifelong learning processes; supporting the development of a long-term adult learning strategy; expanding opportunities for adult learning, etc

Keywords: *lifelong learning, continuing education, adult education, educational policy, Turkey*

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1. Introduction

Relations between Turkey and EU society, especially in the modern world, have a long historical basis. In order to improve, the quality of Turkey's education system was irrevocably endorsed in the 1960s and at the 1999 Helsinki Summit as part of efforts to optimize candidate status. While in the process of full membership in the EU, Turkey continues to adhere to international norms and standards and meet the established conditions [1].

Lifelong learning in Turkey has a long history. Arguments that learning cannot be limited by time and place, that it can take place at any time in human life, in any place where a person lives or communicates, that infinite respect should be shown even to one who teaches one letter that what has been learned is the most important aid, has existed, has been recognized as valuable and has been used in some way in Turkish culture for many years and even centuries. However, in Turkey, as

in other countries, the concept of lifelong learning is seen as a model of approach to education and training [2].

2. Literary review

The problem field of the scientific research was chosen in accordance with the directions of scientific research of the van Ziazium Institute of Pedagogical Education and Adult Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine. The purpose of this literature review is to analyze how lifelong learning policy will continue to change in the coming years, as well as to gain insight into the impact of politics on the effectiveness of lifelong learning in Turkey. Thus, the sources, cited by most other scholars, were selected, so that only reliable articles and journals were usually used.

Turkey's Adult Education System (AE) needs to be restructured from a multidimensional management perspective, from policies to structural changes and rules that are needed in the organizational structure. The study

of literary research gives reason to believe that they are mainly focused on educational qualities. However, no study has been found in the literature on the specifics of the AE system in the future, which aims to increase citizen participation in AE processes, develop adult skills and solve existing problems in the AE system in Turkey. In this context, there is a need for a flexible and sustainable system in the field of AE in Turkey, which is compatible with codes of change and where all available resources are used to the maximum and efficiently [3].

To this end, a group of Turkish scholars [4] studied institutional efforts to support and disseminate adult education in Turkey. The result was the outline of recommendations for strengthening the system of vocational education and training in the context of the implementation of the concept of lifelong learning:

- Institutional system and infrastructure of changes in the horizontal plane, integration between public sectors and social partners.
- Inclusion of formal education, business market, information education, civil society and culture.
- Improving the system and the identity of the system at the regional and local levels.
- Collection of data for comparison and active use to define and evaluate policies.
- Update legal provisions and simplify legislation.
- Research, analysis and systematic evaluation.
- Capacity building in both professional and non-governmental organizations.
- Involvement of non-governmental organizations and other social partners.
- Formation of a culture of learning [4].

In the 21st century, lifelong learning is one of the key pillars of education, closely intertwined with human development and financial growth. Today's world has profoundly influenced the phenomena of globalization, which, as described by Scholte (2001), consists of "processes, as a result of which many social relations are relatively separated from territorial geography, so human lives are increasingly played out in the world as one place" [5].

It is noteworthy, that large universities, governments and non-governmental organizations around the world continue to discuss lifelong learning practices. [6]. Thus, in September 2006, a LifeLong Learning Strategy Document was prepared to follow the policy of lifelong learning in Turkey. Lifelong learning is defined in the document as all types of learning activities of individuals, individual, social, regardless of their professions or not, at schools, universities, at home, at work in any part of society, covering all information and skills for self-improvement of personality

EU politicians have understood the importance of education and training in today's information society and knowledge economy, so they highlight the Union's strategy as cooperation and learning from each other. In 2000, EU education and training policy gained momentum and accelerated, following the adaptation of the Lisbon Strategy. The Union's program focuses on growth of jobs. As global competition grows, information and innovation will become Europe's most important values in education. The Union's long-term strategic objectives for education and training are as follows:

- Implementation of lifelong learning and mobility.
- Improving the quality and effectiveness of training.
- Development of equality, social cohesion and active citizenship.
- Improving creativity, innovation and entrepreneurship in all types and levels of education and training (Europa, 2010) [4].

Lifelong learning approaches contribute to significant individual control over what is studied, as well as the time, place and method of learning. In addition, it is emphasized, that students not only acquire formal skills and qualifications, but also develop motivation to learn and skills to manage their own learning. That is why the introduction of lifelong learning must be accompanied by the adjustment of education systems: the system must be "student-led", or in other words, the student must be placed at the center of the education system. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development notes that it is difficult to understand how learning systems that have been adapted to the requirements of lifelong learning can work without highly developed information and advice systems [7].

However, this problem is not yet the subject of productive and systematic research.

3. Research aim and tasks

The aim of the study is to analyze the features of the implementation of lifelong learning policy in Turkey.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

1. To summarize Turkey's progressive experience in implementing lifelong learning policies.
2. To outline perspective directions of development of adult education in Ukraine on the basis of generalization of vectors of expansion of opportunities for adult learning in Turkey.

4. Materials and methods

To achieve the goals and objectives of the study, there were used:

- method of content analysis of literary sources;
- method of conceptual and categorical analysis to determine and justify the concept of lifelong learning in European and Turkish contexts;
- methods of analysis, synthesis, generalization to substantiate the results.

5. Research results and discussion

Although Turkey's involvement in the concept of lifelong learning is a recent development (2009), the prospect of lifelong learning has a long history. The concept of lifelong education, which was vaguely included in the educational discourse during the 1970s of the twentieth century and used as a tool to integrate formal, non-formal and informal education during the 1980s, was introduced in the context of employment-driven training with a human capital approach in the 2000s [8].

The concepts of lifelong learning and adult education in the process of EU harmonization are widely used today; however, these concepts have been of great importance in the history of education in the Republic of Turkey in the process of national development and mobilization. The first systematic movement related to education began with the congress of the Ministry of Education

in Ankara on July 15, 1921. Sharing his observations and experiences related to education, Gazi Mustafa Kemal stood by the principles of the work that needs to be done, instructing educators to perform other tasks.

After the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, an educated society was the only prerequisite for perpetuating the formation, survival and development of a new form of government. Primary education had to be spread among the people of the country who were tired of the protracted and difficult war. In this connection, on March 3, 1924, in accordance with the Law on the Unification of Education, all educational institutions were involved in the Ministry of Education. The first official organization for adults, called the Department of Public Decency, was established on March 25, 1926 under the authority of the Ministry of Education under the Law on Organization No. 789. In the first years of the republic, the conducted education policy had three main objectives, which were as follows:

1. Ensuring the unity of national culture.
2. Promoting civic education.
3. Training of qualified people, needed by the Republic of Turkey.

In the late 1960's of the twentieth century, the term "non-formal education" arose from the need to meet the changing demands of education and became an alternative for young people and adults in the 3rd world to support formal education institutions with a growing population. In addition, it was also used to address social needs, such as health, nutrition and unemployment. In fact, it was an education, known and used outside of schools, but it was formalized [4].

The first curriculum for primary schools in Turkey was prepared in 1926. It aimed to bring up and educate effective people compatible with their environment. In the 1960s of the twentieth century with the permission of the Ministry of National Education (MNE), non-formal adult education was given a guardian, called the Main Department of Public Education. Later in 1977, it was renewed and redefined as the General Directorate of Non-Formal Education. In 1983, it was renewed again to cover the responsibility for career training, and was renamed the General Directorate of Apprenticeship Training and Non-Formal Education. The Directorate has the greatest responsibility for adult education in Turkey.

In addition, the University of Anadolu is the first institution to introduce an open and distance learning system that serves modern distance education in Turkish distance education. Articles 5 and 12 of Law 47 2547 on Higher Education, which reconfigured Turkish higher education, re-entered into force, which was entrusted to the University of Anadolu, which developed scientifically and technologically on July 20, 1982 by Decree No. 41. The University of Anadolu made a major breakthrough in open and distance education, however, today most universities also offer distance education in Turkey. In the field of adult education, both the Ministry of Education and the Lifelong Learning Centers of Higher Education are continuing their educational efforts to support the country's citizens in adapting to the age, in which they are, and in this harmony, to they felt adaptable, modern and happy. The following table provides statis-

tics on those who continued non-formal education in 2003–2009 [8].

Article № 42 of the Constitution of the Republic of Turkey states that "No one shall be deprived of the right to education and training", emphasizing that education is a fundamental right of citizens. In addition, it is important to continue education throughout life. In addition to educating young people, it is an educational responsibility to take the necessary steps to ensure that adults have a continuing education that helps them meet the importance of both adult learning and government accountability.

Ensuring literacy of citizens outside the age of compulsory primary education

The Professional Qualifications Institutions Act No. 5544 (2006) leads to the introduction of professional standards and non-formal education for qualifications (2009). In this context, lifelong learning and adult education derive from the Constitution and the Basic Law on National Education, and have become a well-known concept in our daily lives. The Law on the Organization and Responsibilities of the Ministry of Education No. 3797 defines the persons to be addressed and the responsibilities of non-formal education. The Vocational Education Act No. 3308 covers all levels and types of vocational education and is related to adult vocational education.

Law No. 2841 regulates that illiterate citizens become literate with a license or diploma. The Law on Professional Qualifications Institutions No. 5544 (2006) leads to the introduction of professional standards and non-formal education for qualifications. The legal framework, OECD membership and the EU integration process help people to learn this concept quickly [8].

Lifelong learning policy in Turkey

The transition to Lifelong Learning from Lifelong Education has in fact been on the agenda of the EU harmonization process and has played a direct and crucial role in restructuring the field of non-formal and adult education. Thus, the field of adult education also quickly adapted to neoliberal transformations, which for a long time continued to affect the school system. Today, the Strategic Documents on Lifelong Learning (MoNE, 2009) and the Action Plan (MoNE, 2014–2018), which regulate the restructuring of non-formal and adult education based on lifelong learning, are generally formulated in line with the Lisbon goals. The Department of Non-Formal Education under the Ministry of National Education (MNE) was reorganized during the same period as lifelong learning.

The national system of public education in Turkey consists of two parts: formal and non-formal. There are five major public educational institutions that provide lifelong learning and training nationwide. These institutions train nearly three million adults annually and retain their social features only externally, not in reality. Opening and organization of courses, curriculum definition, monitoring and evaluation of courses is carried out by the Ministry centrally. In addition, there are fewer public and private institutions, municipalities and non-governmental organizations that provide lifelong learning opportunities.

The Lifelong Learning Strategy was created to restructure both public and private adult education, as well as non-formal education fields. The basis of this strategic document is the basic discourse of globalization, and the key concept here is "change". The document highlights the "Development of information and communication technologies that change lifestyles, learning and work", as well as how learning should continue throughout life [8].

In addition, the discourse of lifelong learning is enhanced by the use of the proverb about learning from the cradle to the grave, which is part of our traditional and authentic learning culture. The goal of the Strategic Document, in line with the Lisbon goals and the European space of lifelong learning, contains perspectives, formulated as "building a lifelong learning system that meets the needs and expectations of Turkish society and ensures the functioning and preservation of this system." Sixteen priorities for the implementation of the goal are related to the creation of mechanisms (restructuring, streamlining, organization and monitoring) in order to maintain and ensure the functioning of the system. The basis of the strategic document emphasizes the link between employment and education. This is clearly seen in the references to projects, excluded under EU coordination. It was noticed, that the focus of creating a lifelong learning system is the formation of the structure of formal, non-formal and adult education, in which the connection with employment is central. Some democratic and political concepts of the European lifelong learning space, such as the creation of a democratic social life and active citizenship, have generally been ignored, with the exception of some trivial references. This fact is not at all surprising, as negotiations with the EU, which began in 2005, have been continued by the neoliberal and neo-Islamic governments of the JDP (the Justice and Development Party, which has been in power for the past 12 years.)

These negotiations, which aim to comprehensively restructure all areas, are very slow, while negotiations on education and culture are relatively faster. The reason for this is the JDP's enthusiasm for the EU's liberalization approach to education. Significant progress is being made in transforming public and "static" formal and non-formal education systems into market-oriented models through consistent neoliberal "reforms". On the other hand, under the JDP, which has become steadily authoritarian, it seems impossible to pursue certain European goals that expand political democracy, such as active citizenship. Thus, the authors note that the current perspective and discourse of lifelong learning in Turkey are more reductionist than the perspective and discourse of the EU, and through lifelong learning is aimed at creating market systems of vocational education and training formally and informally [8].

Therefore, some steps are being taken at a rapid pace to strengthen the link between employment and education. Many multilateral projects, entitled "Modernization of Vocational Education and Training", are embedded in the concept of lifelong learning, a council and system of professional competence are structured, a

group of social partners from the business community is created. The second level of formal education to meet flexible labor demand in the markets was adapted to this process in 2012. Privatization in vocational and technical secondary education has accelerated. The Lifelong Learning Action Plan 2014 is in fact designed to adapt non-formal and adult education to this process.

There is no doubt that the connection between education and employment, which this reductionist and instrumental strategy of lifelong learning presupposes, is directly related to the objective interests of the capitalist class. But there is a significant problem with the reality of Turkish capitalism; chronic unemployment, a huge increase in the number of unemployed graduates, an economy that does not create jobs, and austerity policies that are always on the agenda. In addition, the problems, arising from the collapse of public education, increase educational inequality, reduce the quality of education, schools and courses, left to chance, illiterate or uneducated masses continue to grow. In this situation, can the real goal of prioritizing vocational education and training be to expand the education market? Today, everyone in Turkey knows that the competence you need to have a job, i.e. the acquisition of knowledge, skills and potential, is rarely the main requirement for getting a job.

Thus, participation in lifelong learning systems, which aim to build a competitive knowledge economy for the EU, in part, even if capitalism in crisis increases the number of unemployed graduates, may have some objective basis. But here in Turkey, people mostly need qualified education, knowledge and skills to increase basic life skills, significant social and political literacy in the direction of the ability to understand the changes that are constantly happening around them [8].

As a result, the lifelong learning strategy has helped to introduce new entrants to the expanded market for certificates and diplomas, focusing on vocational education and training. The above documents adhere to the European approach to lifelong learning, which is based on the concept of inquisitive and skillful personality [8].

The documents, guiding the lifelong learning policy in Turkey, are formulated in strict accordance with the hegemonic neoliberal tendencies of that period. Some principles of the Turkish education system, such as equal access, the right to education, equal opportunities, scientific education, joint learning and general education, can help the country adapt to the EU education sector, but all of these principles also suffer from education liberalization and Islamization.

Although Turkey is a political candidate on the periphery of the EU, economic, social and cultural indicators suggest that it should be classified as a developing country, namely a "southern country". Failure to accept this fact leads to an inability to find a realistic solution to the problems, facing Turkey. The Lisbon goals are important in the European reality. Therefore, for Turkey, where literacy, participation in education at all levels, life expectancy and per capita national income are low, in order to go hand in hand with the EU, it is necessary to

have a very strong policy of justice and equality in education, as well as cultural and social policy [8].

To this end, the vectors of empowerment for adult learning were outlined, namely:

- the need for a long-term vision and adult learning strategy, which is more visible in the broader lifelong learning strategy and the Education Vision to 2023.

- Comprehensive and thorough review of adult learning policies and practices in Turkey to support the development of a long-term adult learning strategy that will help identify underdevelopment in certain areas, such as education and training of low-skilled adults, or in selected regions.

- the need to review current funding for adult learning and funding schemes, as well as balancing the overall education budget in favor of adult learning [9].

- simplifying the structure of the diplomacy-based curriculum for non-formal education, while protecting basic skills.

- use of high-level distance learning technology to reach different target groups and increase access to learning in lifelong learning processes.

- updating and diversifying lifelong learning programs for professional, social and cultural skills, conducting a study of social consciousness for lifelong learning processes.

- creation of the National system of monitoring of lifelong learning, which contains data of institutions and organizations, operating in the field of lifelong learning.

- strengthening the procedure for the recognition of certificates in the process of lifelong learning and non-formal education within the MNE, depending on certain standards.

- updating programs to support parents of young, older children and adolescents.

- organization of awareness training in cooperation and coordination with relevant ministries and agencies in the context of combating violence, especially against children and women.

- dissemination of information trainings on combating all addictions for all segments of society, especially children and youth.

- organization of training to raise awareness and develop skills of multi-literacy (digital, financial, health, environment and social media, etc.) among the skills of the XXI century [10].

This study does not take into account the differences in the specifics of the implementation of lifelong

learning policies in Turkey at the central, regional and local levels, which may complicate the generalization of these results.

Prospects for further research may be the creation of a National Lifelong Learning Monitoring System in Ukraine, which contains data from institutions and organizations, operating in the field of continuing education and adult education.

6. Conclusions

1. The generalization of the progressive experience of Turkey made it possible to identify the features of the implementation of lifelong learning policy, namely:

- ensuring the unity of national culture;
- implementation of a strong policy of justice and equality in education;

- promotion of civic education;
- active participation in lifelong learning systems in order to build a competitive knowledge economy for the EU;

- promoting the skills of multi-literacy of Turkish citizens;

- training of qualified people, needed by society;

- adaptation of non-formal and adult education to lifelong learning.

2. The generalization of the vectors of empowerment for adult learning in Turkey made it possible to outline promising areas for the development of adult education in Ukraine, namely:

- investing funds to expand and diversify learning spaces or opportunities in the field of lifelong learning;

- updating programs to support parents of young, older children and adolescents;

- organization of trainings on raising awareness and skills of literacy;

- recognition of certificates in the process of lifelong learning and non-formal education;

- conducting research on social consciousness for lifelong learning processes;

- supporting the development of a long-term strategy for adult learning;

- expanding opportunities for adult learning, etc.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

References

1. Köksal, O., Yildirim, T., Özdemir, O. (2013). The Reflection of the Educational Policies of the European Union to Turkish Education System in Terms of Turkey-Eu Integration. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 18 (6), 803–809. Available at: [https://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr18\(6\)13/10.pdf](https://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr18(6)13/10.pdf)
2. Lifelong Learning Strategy Paper. Ministry Of National Education. Ankara-Turkey. Available at: http://www.ikg.gov.tr/wp-content/uploads/pdf/LLL_Strategy_Paper_Turkey_2009_July.pdf
3. Dilbaz, E. (2021). Rethinking Adult Education In Turkey: The Proposal Of AEP Model. *European Journal of Alternative Education Studies*, 6 (12), 116–150. doi: <http://doi.org/10.46827/ejae.v6i2.3954>
4. Kayman, E. A., Ilbars, Z., Artuner, G. (2012). Adult Education in Turkey: In Terms of Lifelong Learning. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 46, 5858–5861. doi: <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.06.528>

5. Öngör, S. (2014). Lifelong Learning Strategies In Turkey/Izmir: The Purpose of Learning and Barriers to Women's Participation. Institute of International Education, 116. Available at: <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:727505/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
6. Tasçı, G., Titrek, O. (2020). Evaluation of Lifelong Learning Centers in Higher Education: A Sustainable Leadership Perspective. Sustainability, 12 (22), 18. doi: <http://doi.org/10.3390/su12010022>
7. Buyuktanir, D., Duke, C., Karasar, N., Tileylioglu, A., Toth, J. Sz. (2006). Driving Force for the Success of Turkey: Lifelong Learning Policy Paper. Labour Market Team SVET. Ankara, 141. Available at: <https://uil.unesco.org/i/doc/lifelong-learning/policies/turkey-driving-force-for-the-success-of-turkey-lifelong-learning-policy-paper.pdf>
8. Sayılan, F. (2015). Critical Reflections on Lifelong Learning Policy in Turkey. Available at: <http://www.jceps.com/wp-content/uploads/2015/03/12-3-6r1.pdf>
9. Policies for human capital development. Turkey: An ETF TORINO Process Assessment (2020). European Training Foundation, 64. Available at: https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2020-02/06_trp_etf_assessment_2019_turkey.pdf
10. Turkey: Lifelong learning strategy (2021). Available at: https://eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-policies/eurydice/content/lifelong-learning-strategy-103_en

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